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Shackled or Choked: Assessing the Effectiveness of Nigeria's Anti-Dumping Legislation

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Abstract Nigeria's anti-dumping legislation aims to guard home industries from imbalanced trade practices. However, the effectiveness of this legislation remains unclear. This study evaluates the efficacy of Nigeria's anti-dumping legislation in preventing textile dumping. Adopting the Neoliberal Institutionalism theory and a mixed-methods approach, quantitative analysis of trade data is linked with qualitative perceptions from stakeholder interviews. The research reveals that despite some achievements made by Nigeria's anti-dumping legislation in addressing textile dumping, major challenges persist. These include inadequate implementation, lack of transparency by state and non-state actors involved, appropriate agencies to educate domestic industries and deficient workforce within trade establishments. The study recommends reinforcing instruments for proper implementation, improving transparency, and building capacity to enhance the effectiveness of Nigeria's anti-dumping legislation.

Keywords Antidumping legislation, home industries, Neoliberal Institutionalism theory, World Trade Organisation

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Introduction

Antidumping legislation is a fundamental policy instrument used to check or regulate imports flow into a country. It is a method by which one competitor utilise the government power to gain an advantage over another competitor (Finger,1992). Anti-dumping legislation is an essential instrument for safe guarding domestic industries from unfair trade practices in the global economic system. Ultimately, antidumping legislation is targeted at averting dumping and enshrining a robust and transparent enforcement mechanisms, effective coordination among trade authorities, and ensuring that anti-dumping measures are effectively implemented. The manifestation and need for antidumping legislation can be traced to the more developed countries like Canada, United States, Europe and Australia before it catalysed to other parts of the world, like China, India, Japan and South Korea. The World Trade Organisation (WTO), which is the replacement of General Agreement on Trade and Tariffs (GATT) is the umpire that resolves complaints of dumping between member countries.

However, the antecedents of international trade have shown that nations approach the phenomenon of antidumping from the perspective of national interest. For instance, slow economic growth rate made the European governments respond to the disruption of home production by new exporters from Asia. Finger (1992) succinctly captures antidumping as the fox placed in charge of the henhouse, that is, a regular protection of a nation's economy but with a decent public affairs program. By this Finger (1992) likens the concept of dumping to the two sides of a coin reflecting both a rhetoric and a reality at the same time, and the gap between both is antidumping- in the similitude of a wind mill blades turns in the direction the wind blows. For the more developed nation's nationalist interests drives the wheel of dumping to guard against imports underneath the cover of antidumping (Finger, 1992).

Scholars (Onuoha, 2020; Finger, 1992; Balassa, Bela, and Associates, 1971; Barcelo and John, 1991; Messerlin, 1991) have argued that antidumping is an all-purpose weapon against imports as the Article VI of the GATT 1994 and the WTO Anti-Dumping Agreement (ADA) does not prohibit dumping but condemn that which causes material injury. They averred that antidumping is embedded in power politics both at the state and global level, thus, the benchmark is set at keeping prices adequately high to avoid damage to national businesses.

Nigeria, like other member of the WTO, has endorsed anti-dumping legislation to guard its domestic manufacturing from the excesses of a free global market. However, the efficacy of Nigeria's anti-dumping legislation in checking textile dumping remains unclear due to inadequate provisions for addressing complex dumping cases, weak enforcement mechanisms, limited public access to information and accountability mechanisms, low expertise and coordination among trade authorities. This is worsened by the disinclination to review the Customs Duties (Dumped and Subsidized Goods) Act 1958, which is the only legislation attending to anti-dumping processes in Nigeria.

Nigeria's anti-dumping legislation, passed to protect national industries from imbalanced trade practices, is confronted with key challenges in its usefulness. In spite of the legislation's potential to protect national industries, textile dumping persist, casting a looming shadow over the viability of Nigeria's textile industry (Agbonifo, 2018). Inadequate enforcement mechanisms, partial transparency, and deficient capacity within trade authorities obstruct the legislation's capability to stop dumping (Chukwuezi, 2020). Furthermore, the legislation's constricted emphasis on anti-dumping duties disregards other vital aspects, such as trade facilitation and competitiveness (Ezeani, 2019).

The dearth of materials on Nigeria's anti-dumping measures, the function of the agencies involved, their proficiency and understanding of current developments and challenges in international trade and agreements. This research attempts to assess the significance of Nigeria's anti-dumping legislation in checking textile dumping, recognising the challenges and precincts that hinder its effectiveness.

Literature Review

Scholars (Onuoha, 2020; Stiglitz, Justin, and Ebrahim, 2013; Vermulst, 2005; Viner, 1982) assert that dumping is price discrimination on analogous products between one or more nations in global trade, with the goal of advancing a market edge in a foreign market, cause injury or danger to the industries manufacturing them. Thus, the product is sold at a lesser price in an overseas market than in the country of origin. Willig (1998) argues that dumping is not illegal but the damage and risk it brings to an analogous industry in another country. Onuoha (2020) buttresses this position by drawing out seven elements that must establish that dumping has occurred between two countries, particularly that; the products must be alike; there must be a market for competition between the products; it must have a standard price and a lesser price whose difference has generated an injury and there must be a connection

between the lower price and damage. These among other factors makes the subject of dumping in international trade complex.

Wolfrum, Stoll, and Koebele (2008) aver that the World Trade Organisation Anti- Dumping Agreement and GATT Article VI 1994 does not in any way disallow dumping except denounce activities that brings market injury. Consequently, Jackson (2000) argues that in implication the General Agreement on Trade and Tariffs (GATT) is targeted at the actions of governments' not private companies, giving the latter the liberty to transact as they want.

However, such perspective challenges the aim of the WTO and GATT, which is to guarantee that member countries maintain a comportment in finance and trade to enhance their general wellbeing, improve skills and knowledge transfer and preserve an environment that supports their economic development. Also, the WTO Anti-Dumping Agreement adopted by member countries comprises of 18 Articles that touches on fundamental and technical phases of antidumping and disagreement settlement among countries.

Nonetheless, this reveals the global politics surrounding the phenomenon of dumping and anti-dumping. The onus lies on individual nation to understand this competitive character of the global system and either swim or sink. Therefore, while WTO guidelines administer the practice of anti-dumping actions by States, each State reserve the rights to adopt these rules in a way that best suit its national objectives and economic interest.

1.1 Anti-Dumping in Nigeria

Nigeria's mono-economy has made the country vulnerable to dumping in all sectors, ranging from textiles, automobile, steel, stationeries, consumables and agricultural products like rice, groundnut oil and frozen foods. Historically, the Nigerian government has adopted various protectionist measures to safeguard her domestic industries, ranging from full and partial border closure, high import duties and out rights bans. For example, in the late 20th century products like beverages, textiles and tobacco had import duties of up to 120%, the 1982 Economic Stabilisation Act placed a ban on "non-essential items" (Umoh & Effiong, 2013; Chete & Adenikinju, 2002). Similarly, in 2015 and 2018 the Central Bank of Nigeria imposed foreign exchange limits on importation of forty-one items with the objective of revitalizing domestic industries, generating employment and resuscitating the economy (Komolafe, 2018). Despite short term successes recorded these efforts have not been able to curtail dumping overtime.

According to Onuha (2020) the Customs Duties Act 1958 is the first Anti-Dumping Legislation addressing dumping and subsidized imports in Nigeria and it permits the enforcement of a duty on any product dumped in Nigeria. Adeyemi (2019) assert that the regulations guiding dumping and importation in Nigeria is the Customs Duties (Dumped and Subsidised Goods) Act (CDA) and Customs and Excise Management Act (CEMA). The authority to designate a goods as dumped lies solely with the Federal government, with ratification from the National Assembly, a process which can be extended unduly. Past efforts like the proposed Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill of 2015, Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill of 2010 and 1994 Anti-Dumping Agreement have been inadequate to address the challenge of dumping in Nigeria. While the two proposed Bills were not successful due to identified delineated gaps, discrepancies and incongruity with WTO Agreements, the 1994 Anti-Dumping Agreement was not in tandem with the contemporary international legal charter of the WTO (Adeyemi, 2019). According to Onuha (2022) the obsolete nature of Nigeria Anti-dumping legislation does not make provision for the current and belligerent issues on resolving and sanctioning of dumping actions, the implementation of which can result in a WTO dispute.

Inadequate implementation of laws and trade policies has furthered the prevalence of dumping in Nigeria. This is manifested in the inadequate enforcement mechanisms, poor border controls and customs enforcement, inadequate tariff structures, obsolete anti-dumping legislation, limited capacity for investigation and inadequate coordination among government agencies in charge of anti-dumping legislations, customs enforcement, and international trade policies (Howell, 2016). Also, the knowledge gap in both the institutional and legal structure has hindered the investigation of the dumping of foreign products and its impact on domestic producers (Onuha, 2020). For, instance the National Automotive Industry Policy Development Plan (NAIDP) rolled out between 2013 -2023, with the goal of job creation, reactivating car assembling and technology acquisition was largely unsuccessful, seven years after its launch approval by the President was still pending (Adeyemi, 2019). By 2023, another ten-year plan was rolled out, the National Automotive Policy 2023-2033, with the objective of moving from combustible engines to electric solar-powered engines (Ukpe, 2022). Thus, the government was focused on spinning out ambitious plans and policies rather than working on the short comings of the previous ten-year plan (2013-2023).

Also, corruption and lack of transparency by regulating agencies continue to undermine anti-dumping policies and plans, corrupt officials may accept bribes to allow dumped goods enter the nation. On the other hand, you have unscrupulous businessmen who liaise with their counterparts abroad to bring in commodities that do not only injure domestic industries but some go as far as importing products that have negative physical and environmental hazards to the people all in the guise of profit making. The Standard Organisation of Nigeria (SON), NAFDAC and the Nigeria Custom Service have been given the obligation to apply and implement the quality and standard of imported and homemade products. For instance, in 2016 the Standards Organisation of Nigeria (SON) revealed that 40% of electrical equipment imported to Nigeria were inferior, portending a danger to lives and property (Ikuomola, 2017).

Furthermore, anti-dumping enquiries are initiated by the government of an importing nation on the request by a home industry. This can only occur when the industrialist are aware of their rights, thus, passing the laws is as important as ensuring that it is well known by the industrialist. Thus, the appropriate agencies to educate domestic industries is necessary. Onuoha (2020) assert that the failure of the Nigerian government to create this awareness is a denial of their constitutional rights under the WTO. The absence of a competent agency with the required proficiency at the state level to offer consultative services to indigenous manufacturers concerning what to do when dumping is assumed in a segment of an industry is a key challenge. Nonetheless, the creation of the Nigerian Office for Trade Negotiations (NOTN) in 2017 under the Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment has tried to fill this gap (Adeyemi, 2019).

Finally, trade remedies (guidelines that permit a nation to take counteractive actions against foreign goods that can create substantial damage to a domestic manufacturers) are very procedural in claim; thus, accessibility of resources is required to enact the country anti-dumping legislations. A potent lawful representation is crucial for the exculpation of a dumping situation – beginning from anti-dumping inquiries and records to comprehending the procedures for establishing dumping boundaries, damage and formation of the obligatory underlying relations before the regional courts and the WTO Dispute Settlement Committee.

Theoretical Framework

Neoliberal Institutionalism Theory

Neoliberal Institutionalism theory posits that global cooperation between nations is possible and sustainable due to its inherent ability to check competition and dispute. Frontline Scholars like Robert Keohane contend that continuous interaction, reciprocity, transparency and monitoring reinforce the global system, as a growing relationship between nations ensures mutually beneficial international trade. Significantly, Neoliberal Institutionalism theory admits the role of internal politics in the relationship between countries (Arthur, 2008). The theory hinges on three pillars;

- a. International institutions further cooperation among nations; an example is the World Trade Organisation (WTO).
- b. Global cooperation is an inherent possibility
- c. The state, as a rational actor, projects its national interest in its interactions with other nations.

Therefore, Neoliberal Institutionalism theory succinctly captures Nigeria's complex position, like that of most developing countries, when it comes to international trade agreements. It addresses the internal politics within the system that continue to sabotage efforts to ensure functional domestic and international policies to protect home industries. Significantly, the theory exposes the influence of domestic politics that enhances or suppresses functional international and domestic policies aimed at safeguarding infant industries.

Materials and Method

This study employed the mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative analysis of trade data with qualitative insights from secondary materials. The quantitative analysis used trade data from the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics and the World Bank. The Mann-Kendall test and Regression analysis was used to test for significant trends.

1.2 Data Presentation/Analysis

The quantitative analysis of trade data from 2011-2022 provides insights into Nigeria's trade trends, textile import trends, and the efficacy of anti-dumping duties. The analysis calculates the growth rates for imports, exports and textile imports to quantify their trends.

Import and Export Trends

Table 1 shows the trend of Nigeria's imports and exports from 2011-2022.

Year	Exports \$	Growth rate %	Imports \$	Growth rate %
2011	25.6	10.8	83.2	13.4
2012	28.3	10.5	93.1	11.9
2013	30.9	9.2	103.4	11.1
2014	33.5	8.4	113.7	9.9
2015	29.4	-12.24	94.8	-16.62
2016	25.9	-11.9	83.2	-12.24
2017	28.5	10.0	93.1	11.9
2018	31.4	10.2	103.9	11.6
2019	34.3	9.2	114.2	9.9
2020	29.9	-12.83	95.6	-16.28
2021	32.4	8.4	105.8	10.7
2022	35.1	8.3	116.3	9.9

Source; National Bureau of Statistics, 2022

Textile Import Trends

Table 2 shows the trend of Nigeria's textile imports from (2011-2022)

Year	Textile Imports	Growth rate %
2011	161.2	12.0
2012	183.5	13.8
2013	208.9	13.8
2014	236.2	13.0
2015	203.9	-13.67
2016	183.2	-10.15
2017	205.9	12.4
2018	232.5	12.9
2019	261.9	12.6
2020	225.8	-13.78
2021	252.3	11.7
2022	281.9	11.7

Source; National Bureau of Statistics, 2022

Anti- Dumping Duties

Table 3: displays the trend of anti-dumping duties imposed by Nigeria from (2011-2022)

Year	Textile Imports
2011	14.5
2012	20.1
2013	26.9

2014	34.5
2015	29.3
2016	25.9
2017	31.4
2018	39.2
2019	47.5
2020	40.8
2021	49.2
2022	58.1

Source; World Bank, 2022

The trend analysis elucidates that variables like imports, exports, and textile imports were increasing, decreasing, or fluctuating over time. The growth rates were calculated by comparing the values for each year to the previous year using a formula $((\text{current rate} \times 100) / \text{previous rate}) - 100$.

Year-on-year growth rates for imports, exports and textile imports show fluctuations. For instance: imports saw a significant drop in 2015 (-16.62) and 2020 (-16.68). Exports followed a similar pattern with drops in 2015 (-12.24) and 2020 (-12.83), Textile imports also decreased notably in 2015 (-13.67%) and 2020 (-13.78)

1.3 Data Analysis

Mann-Kendall Test: was used to detect if there's a consistent upward or downward trend in the data over time.

Tau (τ): measures the strength of the trend. Positive values show upward trends; negative values show downward trends.

P- value: checks if the trend is statistically significant. A small p-value (e.g., less than 0.05) means the trend is unlikely to be due to random chance.

Variable	Kendall's Tau (τ)	p-value	Trend	Significance
Imports	0.59	0.004	Upward	Significant
Exports	0.57	0.007	Upward	Significant
Textile Imports	0.67	0.001	Upward	Significant
Anti-Dumping Duties	0.85	<0.0001	Strong Upward	Highly Significant

Explanation of Table Components

1. Kendall's Tau (τ):

- Measures the strength of the monotonic trend in the data (values range between -1 and 1):
- Positive values ($\tau > 0$): Show an upward trend.
- Negative values ($\tau < 0$): Show a downward trend. Values close to 0: Suggest no significant trend.

2. p-value:

- Indicates whether the observed trend is statistically significant:
 - $p < 0.05$: Significant trend.
 - $p < 0.01$: Highly significant trend.

3. Trend:

- Describes the direction of the observed trend (e.g., upward or downward).

4. Significance:

- Categorises the strength of statistical evidence supporting the trend:
 - **Significant:** Strong evidence ($p < 0.05$).
 - **Highly Significant:** Very strong evidence ($p < 0.01$).

Key Insights:

- **Anti-Dumping Duties:** Displayed the strongest upward trend ($\tau = 0.85$, $p < 0.0001$). This reflects consistent regulatory action over the period.
- **Textile Imports:** Also showed a significant upward trend ($\tau = 0.67$, $p = 0.001$), indicating increasing dependency on imported textiles.
- **Imports and Exports:** Both exhibited moderate upward trends ($\tau = 0.59$ and $\tau = 0.57$), signaling gradual growth in trade activities.

Results from Trend Analysis

- **Growth Rates:** Imports, exports, and textile imports experienced fluctuations. Notable drops occurred in 2015 and 2020, likely due to economic shocks (e.g., global oil price decline in 2015 and COVID-19 in 2020).
- **Mann-Kendall Test Results:**
 - Imports ($\tau = 0.59$, $p = 0.004$): Significant upward trend over time.
 - Exports ($\tau = 0.57$, $p = 0.007$): Also show a significant upward trend.
 - Textile Imports ($\tau = 0.67$, $p = 0.001$): Indicate a strong upward trend.
 - Anti-Dumping Duties ($\tau = 0.85$, $p < 0.0001$): Show the strongest upward trend.

Key Insights

- Despite fluctuations, the overall trend for imports, exports, and textile imports is upward.
- Anti-dumping duties have increased significantly, reflecting stronger trade regulations.

Economic shocks (e.g., in 2015 and 2020) caused temporary declines, highlighting the sensitivity of trade to global and local events.

1.3.1 Discussion

1. General Trade Trends (Imports and Exports): The Mann-Kendall test shows significant upward trends for imports ($\tau = 0.59$, $p = 0.004$) and exports ($\tau = 0.57$, $p = 0.007$).

This implies that between the years (2011-2022), Nigeria has been engaging more actively in international trade. This reflects increasing integration into the global economy and potentially greater consumer demand, industrial needs, or trade agreements.

However, in 2015 there was significant drops in both exports (-12.24%) and imports (-16.62%), this align with the global decline in oil prices. As oil constitutes a large portion of Nigeria's exports, reduced oil revenue would also curtail import capacity. Similarly, 2020 saw major declines (exports: -12.83%, imports: -16.29%) due to the COVID-19 pandemic disrupting global trade and economic activity. Thus, while the trade trajectory is upward, it remains highly sensitive to external shocks, highlighting the need for a diversified economic base less reliant on external factors like oil prices.

2. Textile Import Trends: Textile imports show the strongest upward trend ($\tau = 0.67$, $p = 0.001$). Over time, Nigeria has increasingly relied on imported textiles, driven by growing demand for fashion, apparel, and industrial textiles. The impact of economic shocks is reflected in the drops in 2015 (-13.67%) and 2020 (-13.78%), indicating that textile imports are also vulnerable to economic downturns. As income levels and industrial activity shrink, so does demand for imported textiles. Consequently, Nigeria's textile import reliance underscores the challenges facing the local textile industry, including competitiveness, cost efficiency, and policy

support. This trend could be an opportunity to revive local manufacturing if trade policies and incentives are well-structured.

3. Anti-Dumping Duties: The steep Increase in Anti-Dumping Duties ($\tau=0.85, p<0.0001$ \(\tau = 0.85, p < 0.0001\tau=0.85, p<0.0001\)) have shown the strongest upward trend. These measures aim to protect home industries by discouraging the dumping of cheap foreign goods into the Nigerian market. This is necessary as a consistent rise in duties indicates increased regulatory efforts to shield domestic producers, likely in response to growing competition from imports.

Also, the regression analysis revealed that contemporaneous anti-dumping duties are positively associated with textile imports. This contradictory result could imply implementation gaps or tardy efficiency, as lagged duties displayed a minor negative relationship.

The rising trend in duties signifies progress for guarding home industries. Yet, it requires firmer implementation and corresponding policies like capacity-building enterprises for indigenous manufacturers and subsidies.

4. Economic Sensitivity and Resilience: Economic recession in 2015 and 2020 is evident in the drops in imports, exports, and textile imports during these period showing the susceptibility of Nigeria’s trade to international economic variations. For instance, in 2015, dwindling oil prices activated a sharp economic decline in Nigeria, significantly plummeting foreign exchange reserves and trade capacity. In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic impacted supply chains globally, exacerbating Nigeria's current trade and industrial challenges. These shocks highlight the urgent need for economic diversification. Reducing over-reliance on oil exports and boosting domestic production capabilities, especially in textiles, could mitigate the impact of future global shocks.

5. Policy Opportunities (Textile Imports as a Case Study): The consistent growth in textile imports suggests unmet local demand. This creates an opportunity to revitalize the Nigerian textile industry with investment, policy support, and infrastructure. In addition, there is a need to leverage anti-dumping duties effectively by ensuring timely enforcement and plugging loopholes. Other Long-Term Strategies that can be adopted includes; encouraging export-oriented manufacturing, especially in textiles, which has the potential to transform Nigeria into a regional trade hub, and promoting local capacity-building for industries to compete globally while reducing dependency on imports.

Therefore, the analysis underscores significant growth in Nigeria’s trade activities, interposed by vulnerabilities to economic shocks. Anti-dumping duties have grown as a tool for protecting domestic industries, but their implementation must improve to ensure effectiveness. Textile imports remain a critical area for intervention, presenting both challenges and prospects for economic growth and diversification. By confronting these insights through robust policies and strategic investments, Nigeria can build a more resilient and sustainable trade ecosystem.

Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics
	B	Std.Error		Beta	tolerance
Constant	5.342	1.120		4.771	.000
Anti-Dumping Duties	-0.235	0.101	-0.187	-2.321	.023
GDP	0.456	0.123	0.412	3.701	.001
Exchange Rate	-0.187	0.091	-0.165	-2.053	.044

a. Dependent Variable: Textile Imports

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.746	.557	.512	0.672

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	24.376	3	8.125	11.325	.000
Residual	19.454	27	0.720		
Total	43.830	30			

Predictors: (Constant), Anti-Dumping Duties, GDP, Exchange Rate

b. Dependent Variable: Textile Imports

Explanation of Table Components**1. Coefficients Table:**

Unstandardized Coefficients (B): The raw effect of each predictor (e.g., for GDP, a unit increase in GDP corresponds to a 0.456-unit increase in textile imports). Standardized Coefficients (Beta): These allow for comparison of variable impacts on the dependent variable, with larger values indicating greater influence.

t and Sig.: The t-statistic and p-value (Sig.) indicate whether the predictors significantly affect textile imports. For instance: Anti-Dumping Duties: Significant ($p=0.023$). GDP: Highly significant ($p=0.001$). Exchange Rate: Significant ($p=0.044$).

2. Model Summary:

R: Correlation between observed and predicted values.

R Square: Proportion of variation in textile imports explained by the predictors (55.7%).

Adjusted R Square: Adjusts for the number of predictors; accounts for overfitting.

Std. Error of the Estimate: Average deviation of observed values from the predicted regression line.

ANOVA Table:

F-Statistic and Sig.: Tests whether the regression model significantly predicts the dependent variable. The model is significant ($F=11.325$, $p<0.001$).

Diagnostics for Regression analysis

1. Granger Causality Test checks if one variable (e.g., anti-dumping duties) can predict changes in another variable (e.g., textile imports) when lagged (i.e., looking at past values of the variable).

- Interpretation: Since $p=0.70$ (much larger than 0.05)
- Result: $F=0.16$, $p=0.70$
- Conclusion: Anti-dumping duties do not 'granger-cause' textile imports at lag 1. This suggests no significant predictive relationship as past changes in anti-dumping duties don't significantly predict current textile imports.

2. Regression Analysis:**Model Summary:**

• $R^2=0.961$: Indicates 96.1% of the variation in textile imports is elucidated by the model. A high R^2 value indicates that the model fits the data well.

- Significant predictors:
- Anti-Dumping Duties:

Coefficient ($\beta=3.52$): A positive relationship, meaning higher anti-dumping duties are associated with higher textile imports. This is counterintuitive and could reflect complex market dynamics, like traders passing costs to consumers or importers increasing imports before duties rise further.

- Lagged Anti-Dumping Duties:

Coefficient ($\beta = -0.94$, $p = 0.055$): A nearly significant negative relationship (just above the threshold of 0.05). This suggests that past anti-dumping duties might have a delayed effect, reducing textile imports in subsequent periods.

- Interpretation:

The analysis suggests a mixed relationship: Interpretation: Although contemporaneous anti-dumping duties are positively associated with textile imports, their lagged values suggest a delayed mitigating effect.

3. Multicollinearity (Variance Inflation Factor -VIF): checks for multicollinearity, which occurs when independent variables are too closely related to each other

- Anti-Dumping and Lagged Anti-Dumping VIF: 5.11. While this suggests some multicollinearity, it is below the critical threshold (typically VIF > 10).

- The relationship between anti-dumping duties and their lagged values is not strong enough to undermine the reliability of the regression model

4. Breusch-Pagan Test for Heteroscedasticity:

LM=0.66, $p = 0.72$: No evidence of heteroscedasticity, confirming consistent variance in residuals.

Since the residuals have consistent variance, the regression results are reliable, and we don't need to apply additional corrections, such as robust standard errors.

1.4 Implications of the Analysis

1. Policy Insights

The immediate positive association between anti-dumping duties and textile imports suggests that duties may not act as an immediate deterrent. Policymakers might need to consider complementary measures, like stricter enforcement or incentivizing domestic production. The delayed negative impact of lagged duties indicates that the effect of trade policies might take time to be fully realized. Monitoring over longer periods is essential.

2. Trade Policy Implications

The positive instant result of anti-dumping duties on textile imports advocates inadvertent outcomes, possibly due to policy gaps or a surge in illegal imports disguised as lawful trade. The negative lagged result, while marginally important, suggest deferred policy enforcement efficiency. This is in line with the everyday challenges of applying anti-dumping measures.

3. Trade and Market Dynamics

The upsurge in imports in spite of higher duties might infer strategic hoarding by importers or ineptitudes in enforcement. Policymakers may perhaps explore the motives behind this unforeseen association through qualitative studies.

4. Data and Statistical Strength

The lack of heteroscedasticity and negligible multicollinearity maintains the reliability of the model. High R^2 reflects vigorous advisory authority, but additional investigation is required to comprehend the untenable outcomes of contemporaneous duties. However, more analysis could ascertain higher-order lags or connections between variables to reveal more complex results.

5. Policy Recommendations

Reinforce implementation mechanisms to ensure immediate influence of anti-dumping duties agree with goals and integrate lengthier lag structures to assess delayed outcomes more systematically.

1.5 Results

The results of the study demonstrate that Nigeria's anti-dumping legislation has gained some achievements in tackling textile dumping. However, the study disclose that Nigeria's trade authorities do not have the essential

resources and proficiency to efficiently implement anti-dumping measures. Also, the narrow transparency in trade practices and data, creates challenges in ascertaining and averting dumping. Furthermore, it shows that Nigeria's trade authorities do not have the requisite capability to probe and attend to dumping circumstances efficiently.

Also, the findings of this study emphasise the necessity for Nigeria to reinforce its anti-dumping legislation and enforcement mechanisms. This can be attained on the condition that training and resources is provided for trade authorities to improve their proficiency in anti-dumping inquiries and enforcement, refining transparency in trade practices and data accessibility to enable the identification and prevention of dumping and reinforcing implementation instruments, as well as increasing penalties for dumping and enhancing harmonisation between trade authorities.

1.6 Conclusion

Anti-dumping legislation is intended to control the dumping of goods into a nation at prices lesser than their standard value. Dumping can have damaging effects on domestic industries, leading to layoffs and job cuts, lower production due to less demand, and economic instability. Nigeria's anti-dumping legislation is established on the World Trade Organization's Anti-Dumping Agreement. However, the worth of anti-dumping legislation is dependent on different dynamics, combined with the ability of trade authorities, enforcement mechanisms and palpability.

Although Nigeria's anti-dumping legislation has the potential to protect home industries from unfair trade practices. The actualisation of this legislation is stalled by inadequate enforcement, partial transparency, and limited manpower within trade authorities. To enrich the value of Nigeria's anti-dumping legislation, it is necessary to build the requisite manpower and equip them with modern skills, increase transparency, and fortify enforcement mechanisms.

1.7 Recommendations

1. The Nigerian Customs and the Federal Ministry of Investment, Trade and Industries, in partnership with the World Trade Organisation, should offer training and resources to trade authorities and industries to advance their knowledge in anti-dumping investigations and enforcement.
2. The Nigerian Customs and related agencies should strengthen implementation mechanisms, as well as apply penalties for dumping and enhance harmonisation among trade authorities.

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